

CenRaPS Journal of Social Sciences

International Indexed & Refereed

ISSN: 2687-2226 (Online)

<https://cenraps.org/journal/>

Original Article

doi.org/10.46291/cenraps.v5i1.95

**Role of Educational Institute in Heritage Management: A Case Study in the
Lalmi-Mainamati Hill Region, Bangladesh**

Md Nazmul Hassan

Post Graduate in Archaeology, Department of Archaeology, Comilla University, Cumilla
– 3506.

Email: nazmulhassan019@gmail.com, Orchid ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2208-6995>

Md. Sadequzzaman

Assistant Professor, Department of Archaeology, Comilla University, Cumilla – 3506.

Email: s.zaman.tan1401@gmail.com

Abstract:

This paper aims to investigate the role of educational institutes in heritage management from the local and national policy level to safeguard archaeological heritage perspectives in the Lalmi-Mainamati area, cumilla, Bangladesh. Lalmi-Mainamati area is one of the historical places in Bangladesh and in this area almost 50 archaeological sites were marked by the department of archaeology (DOA), and most of the sites represent our historical remains from 6th to 13th century CE. The Department of archaeology maintained all of these sites under antiquity act 1968 but the drawback of manpower resources and financial budget is that most of the sites are unprotected and lack proper maintenance process. Local people, tourists, Fanatic society, and mischievous people are ruining our historical past evidence in many ways. From the causes of these casualties, people are not aware of it and they are not realizing the importance of our heritage practicing and safeguarding lack of proper information & instruction when they visit these historical places or are attached somehow with these archaeological sites. This paper deals with how our educational institute can play a vital role in safeguarding archaeological heritage in many ways perspectives on the Lalmi-Mainamati area.

Keywords: Public Archaeology, Heritage Management, Educational Institute, Heritage Safeguarding, Lalmai-Mainamati

1. Introduction:

There are many ways to heritage management and safeguarding of past remains. Stakeholder engagement is one the easiest and effective ways to protect our heritage and spread heritage value to mass people in our community. More specifically, educational organization can massive change in mass people engagement, awareness and connectivity with our heritage. An educational institute is a place where people of different ages gain knowledge and a large variety of perceptions with proper realization as a human (Brown, 2017). They are also concerned with our Societies sub-disciplines like Social norms & Behaviors, Culture, social activity, etc. In addition, Education is a gradual process that brings positive changes in human life and behavior. It's a process of gaining knowledge through collaboration with theoretical knowledge and other outreach activities (Shrivasta, 2016). According to sustainable development goal (SDG4), Authority ensure 100% quality and equitable primary and secondary education without cost and by 2030 in Bangladesh (Ahmed et. all, 2013). On the other hand, Heritage is a representative part of our culture, human origin history and chronological development. Heritage is an important part of cultural activity and it belongs to a present society for understanding how our society is involved with humans. So if it will protect our next generation, they are aware and concerned about their history. Besides this public engagement and awareness give us a positive outcome to connect with the past remains. The basic idea about collaboration for heritage protection and management is identifying and legitimizing the stakeholders (Ass, Ladkin & Fletcher,2005) that are connected with development and management (Bott, Grabowski, & wearing,2011). In collaboration with educational organization with heritage is significant role in site protection and management. In Bangladesh, Most of the people are unconsciously visiting historical places with lack proper guidance and information delivered opportunities. They miss historical background and proper explanation about importance of heritage. As a result it is not touch emotionally to them. According to this point, educational institutes can play a vital role through formal and informal education and some policy-making changes in national curriculum. Furthermore, Government should take initiative at a massive level activity to represent our heritage all over the world. In this paper, we are suggesting

how educational institutes impact on heritage management and what they should take initiative for maintenance and proper safeguarding in heritage management. The Department of Archaeology (DOA) Bangladesh in the last 50 years working on heritage engagement, maintenance and safeguarding but lack proper financial budget, resources of manpower and proper documentation and protection that are ruinous day by day. Besides this People are demolishing these sites unconsciously and they are not aware and care about their heritage adequately.

2. Aim and Objectives

The research paper aims to identify the role of potential stakeholder Educational institute and their possible role in the heritage management of the Lalmai-mainamati hills area. It also intend to develop a sustainable heritage preservation model and management plan in collaboration with educational institution filed. Moreover, this model introduce a new dimension of create heritage field professional, community involvement and young generation engagement for long term plan in the field of heritage management. Finally, the research is expected to be beneficial for researchers who are working in the area of academic, organizational and activity based long term contribution Heritage management in Bangladesh.

3. Methodology

The study concentrates on the role of educational institutes and their activity to increase heritage awareness, Stakeholder engagement, heritage safeguarding in Lalmai-mainamati region. This research paper is based on the analysis of different educational institutions and their role in promoting heritage, and social awareness among students, community people, and visitors. This research paper uses a qualitative approach to analyze the potential role of educational institutes in heritage management and tourism development in the Lalmai-mainmast Hills area. Qualitative methods involve collecting data through interviews, surveys, focus groups, or observations that are then analyzed for patterns and themes. The researcher will use this method to identify potential ideas and possibilities involved with the site's preservation efforts as well as their roles in sustainable management practices such as communication, engagement activities like raising awareness campaigns, Employment community people, etc., which can help protect its cultural value from irreversible damage. Moreover, to present data some tools are used during this research like: ARCGIS, Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Illustration and Mobile GPS Application etc.

4. A case study of the Lalmai-Mainamati Hills area, Bangladesh.

The Lalmai-Mainamati is located about 8 kilometers to the west of Cumilla city. The Lalmai-Mainamati hill range is 18 kilometers long (from north to south), 4.5 kilometers wide at its widest point (from east to west), and can reach a maximum height of 45 meters. The hill range contains a number of archaeological sites, some of which have previously been excavated and preserved. Between the fourth and the twelfth centuries CE, this area was part of a cultural and political sub-region named Samatata. The region, comprising the trans-Meghna basin, was adjacent to the Harikela sub-region. The sites and surroundings of the vibrant landscape, forests, rivers, and the people in and around this important center of Mahayana Buddhism from around the 7th to the 13th centuries CE are described elaborately in the epigraphic records. The seven viharas, temples, stupas, and shrines that were excavated represent the glorious past of this region.

The Lalmai-Mainamati hill range is one of the important archaeological areas which are enlisted in “Updating the UNESCO World Heritage Tentative List of Bangladesh, 2021” for outstanding universal value based on the Criterion (ii): to exhibit an important interchange of human values, over a span of time or within a cultural area of the world, on developments of architecture or technology, monumental arts, town-planning or landscape design; Criterion (iv): be an outstanding example of type of buildings, architectural or technological ensemble or landscape which illustrates (a) significant stage(s) in the human history; Criterion (v): be an outstanding example of a traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture (or cultures), or human interaction with the environment especially when it has become vulnerable under the impact of irreversible change. With the discovery of copper plate inscriptions of many dynasties that primarily belonged to Buddhist religious traditions, the dynastic history of this sub-region is thoroughly established. The ruling dynasties are the Gupta dynasty (c. 4th to 6th centuries CE), Natha dynasty (early 7th century CE), Rata dynasty (c. 7th century CE), Khadga dynasty (from the latter part of the 7th to 8th century CE), Early Deva dynasty (latter part of the 8th to 9th century CE), Chandra dynasty (latter part of the 9th to 11th century CE), Varman dynasty (latter part of the 11th to 12th century CE) and Later Deva dynasty (c.13th century CE). Most archaeological sites are impacted by the recent growth of construction, habitation activities, and the natural decay process. Human activity is changing the landscape more and more in a country like Bangladesh with a high population. Major tourist destinations can be found at these locations as well. All these activities cause the place to suffer substantial harm as a result. It is essential to take action to save cultural

heritage in such a circumstance. For the preservation of cultural heritage, digital techniques provide precise and appropriate data. The major goal of this study is to investigate and experiment with digital approaches employed in documentation to assure heritage protection, monitoring, and propound digitally for a better knowledge of the archaeological history of Lalmai-Mainamati.

Figure 01: Maps of present study area which cover sites distribution and recent infrastructural changes at the Lalmai-Mainamati hills area.

5. Educational Institute and Heritage Management.

Educational institute is responsible for systemic exchange of knowledge, skills and cultural values within formally structure besides this they gather knowledge form several kind of activity which conduct on informally. So an educational institute or organization create the opportunity to know thyself and others information which change to our society. The major trends seen in heritage focus to values community based approaches (Askew and logan 1994:5; Logan 2010; ICCROM 2013). The world heritage system moved to valued based education system and they focus on possible

opportunities to engaging community people and stakeholder for heritage maintenance (Logan and Wijesuriya, 2016). In collaboration with educational institute with heritage a multiple model proposed in different times recently UNESCO worked on community based heritage learning program, Youth connectivity leadership program and others activity focus on heritage awareness in mass people.

Table 01: Convention and Legislation Focus on Educational Program and Heritage Managements.

sl. No.	Year of Announcement	Charter/ Announcement name	Location of the wording	Focus on this term
01	1956	Delhi Charter	Article 12	To enhance affection and respect about our heritage authority should announce several heritage engagement based educational program and also create opportunity to join archaeological excavation, exploration, guide tour training, heritage exhibition, writing competition and others educational activity.
02	1987	Washington Charter	Article 15	Authority should design program to encourage and participated from the beginning with children of ages.
03	1990	Lausanne Charter	Article 9	It is urgent to create international mechanism for the exchange of information and experience among professional and tertiary education level for medium and long term planning.
04	1996	Segesta Announcement	Article 1 & Article 2	Article 1, Focus on training for creating specialist (Archaeologist, architect, art historian and others) for heritage management and promoting exchange of know how. Article 2, To enhance communication, information sharing , encouraging mass people, branding and promotion authority should be focus on educational curriculum, seminar and others activity to community people for learn heritage presentation and explanation to mass people.
05	1999	Mexico Charter	Article 1.3, Article 5.4, Article 5.5 & Article 5.6	Article 1.3, Interpretation and presentation program should be facilitate and encourage the high level of public awareness for long term heritage management. Article 5.4, Tourism program should be focus on employment of guide and site interpreter from host community to enhance skill of community people.
06	1972	Parris Convention	Article 5(c), 5(e)	Article 5(c) & 5(e) focus on enhance capacity building about technical and scientific skill on heritage preservation and share those ideas through education and information sharing process.
07	2005	Faro Convention	Article 13	Focus on professional training, exchange of knowledge and skill development activities for heritage safeguarding.

To enhance educational activity in heritage management researcher are suggesting multiple model and perspective. According to Jhon evans, Archaeology and heritage was extreme popular in local community though still now most of the people are misguided about this field lack of information available. Formal education and mass people awareness change this figure (Evans, 1975). Educational institute easy to access in community level and sharing ideas with community people about heritage (Corbishely et al, 2008,2012; cracknel and corbishley 1986; Henson et al. 2004, 2006; jameson 2003; planel 1996). In addition, Archaeological charter and announcement focus on educational activity in heritage management. For instance, Delhi Charter,1956; Washington charter 1987; Lausanne charter 1990 focus on heritage engagement based education program, exchange program, create opportunity for student in archaeological excavation, exploration and post field work analysis. Moreover, Segesta announcement, 1996; Maxico charter 1999; parries convention 1972 mentioned on training program for community people, employment opportunity, community people based education and training facilities opportunity for better heritage management. In the Lalmai-Mainamati hills area several stakeholders are connect with heritage in different perspective. So upon this discussion educational institute impact is very much significant for heritage management and in this paper we talk about the Lalmai-Mainamati region educational institute contribution and possibilities in heritage management.

6. Educational Stakeholders and their possible role in heritage management

An educational institution is a place where people of different ages gain knowledge including several types of co-curriculum activity. So it will be a perfect place where people are gaining theoretical knowledge including practical experience. Generally, educational institutions have had two types of education methods: formal & informal education. If we are able to collaborate both methods at a time it will have a positive role in human life. Heritage is part of our past culture and we have had a responsibility to take care of this. So if our educational institute makes proper plans and concerns there will be massive changes in community people and the young generation. So Educational institutes and their activity play a vital role to heritage awareness and safeguarding their positive role and them also engage the young generation with our heritage to protect for the future generation. It also helps to impact their mind subconsciously protecting and branding their cultural heritage nationally and internationally in the future. Sustainability, development, and public awareness of our heritage educational institutes play a vital role to protect and clear

concepts. The Lalmai-mainamati region is a popular archaeological and natural tourist spot. A large number of archaeological heritage historically significant uncovered this area besides this natural beauty. Various types of people live surrounding this area and they lead their regular life.

Figure 02: Educational institute and Organization Distribution on the Lalmai-Mainamati Hills Area.

The Lalmai Mainamati hills area several educational institutes developed in previous few decades because of the natural beauty and available space in this area. A huge number of students from various places come there to complete their educational studies from primary to higher studies and various people come to the national and international level to visit ancient educational institutes as part of their informal educational learning. In this paper, we are discussing possible roles to our educational institute for heritage management in the Lalmai-Mainamati region.

6.1. Mainamati Museum

Museums have historically seen as cultural institutions whose prime goal are education and learning (Omar et. al, 2018). In last few decades, museum are aware to add value to their community economically, culturally and multiple perspective and represent the relation with their own history and others cultures and people (Lumley, 1988; 2). Museums play a vital role in engaging visitors and understanding the cultural value of our heritage. A Museum is considered as an important educational institute for a wide range of public outreach activities where they can take initiative for public awareness and engagement to protect our heritage. Mainamati museum- Situated middle of the Lalmai-Mainamati hills - organizes several types of community engagement activity and heritage awareness programs like: Museum day, National Day celebration, Antiquities exhibition, Museum guide facilities etc. Apart from this, a significant number of visitors come to museum from home and abroad for visiting museum objects and they also visit archaeological sites which locate in surrounding area. Museum authority should initiative to enhance relation between museum object and visitors through multiple approach such as digital documentary show, discussion on heritage significant and relation between human and object. Furthermore, they can arrange events like archaeology day, Museum day, world Heritage day and heritage quiz competition, Public speaking etc. Visitors & local people join this type of activity and they are concerned about their heritage & culture.

6.2. Primary School

Primary education is free and compulsory in Bangladesh (Rahman, 2020). So most of the children get this opportunity to continue their primary education & after that most of the people drop out of their education journey. So primary education institutes can play a significant role to introduce our heritage and historical past story. The Lalmai-Mainamati region has a number of primary school (Shalbon primary school, bard school, unique school, Government laboratory, salmanpur primary school, kindergarten etc.). Department of Archaeology (DOA) regional office can take

initiative to design capacity building and training for trainer workshop for primary teachers to enhance heritage education knowledge and deliver method to their student. Moreover, in primary level they arrange heritage drawing, Heritage adventure gaming, Heritage storytelling event etc. it will make them aware and engage with heritage from the beginning of their life.

6.3. Secondary & Upper secondary School

Secondary education in Bangladesh is the bringing stage of a child. Generally, 11 and 16 years old students study in this phase and upper secondary education is at the age of 16 and 19 years. In this stage, students engage in multiple curricular activities and they enjoy learning new skills, exploring new areas of knowledge, and preparing for future journeys. During this time they realized a new world in front of them. So if we are able to understand that heritage value and their functional importance in their journey it will help them to engage with their culture and heritage. The charter of United Nation, Article 1 Purpose and function of secondary education is promoting education, science and culture and strongly commitment to education for all (Charter of the united nation, 1945). The Lalmai-Mainamati hill region develop with high schools and colleges like govt. Laboratory high school, Ispahani school & college, Bard High School, Comilla Cadet College, Shalbon High school, cantonment high school, Comilla city college, Comilla Cambrian college lalmai degree college, etc., .Besides their regular academic activity they can arrange Heritage oriented co-curricular activity like: debate, symposium, excursion, heritage tour, awareness programed, online & offline heritage photography competition etc.

6.4. Universities

Universities are recognized as platform for open discussion, knowledge sharing and ideas. They gain reputation and trust in several ways. They can be influential in the area of cultural history and impact upon young mind (Jokilehto, 2006). In the world perspective, several university play significant role in heritage management. For instance, the public university of Al Quds, Israel enhance heritage conservation through their activity (Safi, 2020). University can enhance heritage management through academic research, seminar and heritage awareness based workshop as a part academic curriculum. Moreover, they also engage in various co-curricular activities to build up their leadership skill, management skill and engage with the various kinds of social, cultural activity. The Lalmai-Mainamati region has some universities like Comilla University, CCN Science and Technology University, Bangladesh Army international university of Science & Technology. Department of archaeology, Comilla University contributes their research on heritage

management policy, Safeguarding methods, and Public archaeological perspective possibilities and proposals. Besides this, students can contribute to the heritage awareness movement, they can arrange Heritage Literacy activities like Published magazines, wallpaper, essay writing competitions, Open discussion forums, etc. As a part of branding and promotion, the university can focus on the Lalmai-Mainamati region heritage-related theme, topic, and public outreach program.

6.5. Religious Center

A religious center is a place where people pray and worship their god. Besides this, they also gain knowledge about their religion. In the Lalmai-Mainamati region, most of the archaeological sites are Buddhist viharas and a few of them are Islamic architecture. Surrounding the archaeological heritage, few religious centers are doing their religious activity and learning centers can play a vital role in safeguarding our heritage. Nabo shalbon vihara opposite side of shalbon vihara can play a significant role in practicing ritual activity at shalbon Bihar. It will help visitors understand the functional aspect of this site. Besides this, there are so many Islamic religious centers so if we are able to understand heritage value and significance to our society they are playing a vital role to protect our heritage. Most of the time fanatic people destroy our heritage but when all of them work together and they are aware of them it will give us positive feedback to safeguard our heritage.

6.6. Training Institutes

Training institute are mainly for professional skill development. People are come on training center to get professional knowledge and enhance skills for career development. Mostly, ages people who are responsible and working their profession come on this place. The Lalmai-Mainamati region has had various training institutes and technical skill learning institutes. Lots of people come on this institute for learning purposes for a very short period. These institutes are like: Technical Training Center, Teachers Training Institutes, BARD, Physical institutes etc. if those institute design a plan besides their training session participants are getting an opportunity to visit and experience their heritage. This program spared heritage knowledge several sector and professional community. Furthermore, Regional office DOA can take initiative to guide service to explain and exhibits heritage object and significant for enhance awareness and connectivity.

7. Role of National level Education Policy Maker

Last fifteen year's department of archaeology has remarkable change in heritage management plan and protect our valuable heritage ruins. Although it is not much more comparative with heritage management condition. Most of the cases lack of human resources, expert professional and financial budget shortage DOA cannot properly effort to protect our heritage. As a matter of fact most of the archaeological sites are abandoned and drastically effected in many ways. The Lalmai-Mainamati hills area most of the visitors are misconception about heritage knowledge (Nazmul, 2022) and they severely affected our heritage unconsciously. From that situation heritage concern should ne focus on national curriculum about this heritage for mass people heritage knowledge.

7.1. National Education Policy

In Bangladesh, primary and secondary education are compulsory for Bangladeshi citizens and it was a positive result to our overall literacy statistics. Heritage knowledge is important for everyone because everyone needs to know their route and it will make them confident and gain experience. So when we are making our national education policy we should focus on our heritage and culture study. It will be the easiest way to make them aware about our heritage and they will be concerned about it when they understand heritage value and why it should be protected for our future generation. In 2010 Bangladesh government published a national education policy but they ignore heritage and culture. If possible to focus on this it will be effective to protect and be aware about heritage and culture. Besides all other academic fields, national education policy makers should be focused on it in future for protection and aware about heritage to our upcoming generation.

7.2. University Grant Commission (UGC)

University is the highest educational institute in Bangladesh. Where the institutes are making subject-oriented expertise and they work on the academic development of their specific sector. In Bangladesh, only two universities study archaeology Jahangirnagar University & Comilla University. So instead of being a large part of our archaeological heritage, our expert person is very low. The university grant commission can work on it and they open different university new departments where students can get opportunities to gain knowledge about heritage & culture and after completion, they serve our country to protect, branding & promote our heritage, culture and explore new eras of our history. Besides this UGC also gets funds for heritage & culture research. It will inspire researchers to work on heritage & culture.

7.3. Cultural Ministry

The culture ministry is part of the government people republic of Bangladesh. Under this ministry various autonomous institutes are there Public libraries, Bangladesh Shilpakala Academy, Bangladesh National Museum, Bangla Academy, Nazrul Institute, National Book center, Bangladesh copyright office, Bangladesh folk arts and crafts foundation and Department of Archaeology. So it was undoubtedly hard to maintain and proper management. Besides this financial budget and resources are not available instead of a large number of archaeological sites in Bangladesh. The government should be more focused on these institutes and inspire heritage protection and route level. The Department of Archaeology also can arrange regional. National & International level seminar, symposium, workshop and conference to know our heritage all over the world.

8. The Role of International Policy Maker's

Heritage is a universal value and its part of our world history & civilization so internationally this sector has some organizations that care about world archaeology, History, and culture. Bangladesh has had two international organizations named UNESCO Bangladesh & ICOMOS Bangladesh but their work is not much more visible from the Bangladesh perspective. Another important thing is this organization is focused only on world heritage sites and they are concerned about this but in Bangladesh, many other sites are also part of the world heritage tentative list but they were not concerned about it.

8.1. UNESCO

UNESCO Bangladesh was established in 1996 to contribute Bangladesh Social, Cultural and economic dimensions to sustainable development through education, culture. Communication & information. The Bangladesh education ministry is the chairperson of this organization so it will be easy to contribute to the heritage and cultural field in collaboration with our education sector. This kind of international organization can support us on national & international policy level and beside this they also work on education based heritage awareness through their agenda to protect our heritage and culture. UNESCO Bangladesh works with the Department of Archaeology at policy level besides this they should focus on grassroots level implementation to protect our heritage.

8.2. ICOMOS

ICOMOS Bangladesh was created to enhance professionalism in the conservation, management, planning and development of our heritage in Bangladesh. It also helps to connect networks all over the world heritage profession. In Bangladesh they are arranging national & international webinar, workshops, expatriates opinion sharing discussion and International day celebration to public engagement and awareness. Beside this they are also working with exchange programed collaboration with UNESCO, IUCN & ICCROM. ICOMOS Bangladesh can collaborate with the Department of Archaeology and local Non-governmental organizations to engage with the public and make them aware about our culture & heritage Protection.

9. Public archaeology through Educational Approach

In recent years, Public Archaeology is one of the popular disciplines in archaeological research. Public archaeology is bridging with archaeology and public to increase public awareness, ownership and heritage as a public property so everybody should protect their heritage. Researcher are represent various aspect about public archaeology however the most important and popular idea was education. Education is the process of learning skill, value, belief, habit and mostly human behavior development so when people are educated in different aspects they can understand heritage value, why it should be protected for our future generation and they also care and work on protecting their heritage. In this paper the researcher discussed the role of educational institutions in the Lalmai-Mainamati region. Lalmai-Mainamati region is a historically and archaeologically renowned area. Besides the Lalmai-Mainamati hill area various types of educational institutes have developed in the last two decades and the tourism industry also developed day by day. If local people (who belong to this area) are concerned about their heritage, we can protect this. Most of the time we do not cover all ages of people to engage with heritage so we can't get sustainable feedback about heritage awareness and protection from the public. If we can manage all education institutes surrounding these places then most of the people are covered and they are aware about their heritage, they realize this as a part of their culture and route. Besides this every year lots of visitor came here to visit this historical places and most of the time they do not get wright information about this places and local people are describe negatively but if local educational institute can arrange heritage promotional and information sharing program as part of co-curricular activity visitor are aware about this sites and they enjoy it. However, we should also focus on our national and international policy making because most of the people have misconceptions about archaeology. They think it's like a dinosaur, Adventure, Surprising

something but when they come on to visit they don't like it. So our national and international policy makers should be focused on introducing archaeology in vast areas and education can play a vital role to implement this. Another important thing is government should give permission to implement International rules & regulation to protect our heritage and our national antiquity act should be updated focus on Public engagement and awareness.

10. Threats and Challenges

This paper the main threats are proper planning on policy level and permission to implement international law & regulation in Bangladesh. Most of the country's public can access heritage maintenance and implement non-governmental organization activity but in Bangladesh without proper permission and procedure people are not able to access our archaeological sites. Another important thing is lack of proper expertise and opinion. We are not getting proper direction so we need to focus on our skilled resources for policy making. The most vulnerable challenge is to unite all of the sector and take a decision collaboratively to protect our heritage. Finally, educational Institutes are part of the education ministry so if they take positive initiative at the policy level and focus on protecting our heritage it can be possible to work and make aware and engage the public with heritage.

11. Conclusion

In Bangladesh, the role of educational institutions in heritage management can be significant, particularly in preserving and promoting cultural heritage sites such as the Lalmai-Mainamati heritage cluster. These institutions can contribute by: Conducting research and survey to gather information about the cultural heritage sites, their history and significance. Providing education and awareness program to student and the local community about the importance of cultural heritage preservation. Offering training and skill development opportunities for heritage management professional, including site managers, conservators and tour guides. Collaborating with governmental agencies, NGO, and local communities to preserve and promote the cultural heritage sites. Rising funds and resources to support heritage management initiatives. In conclusion, By taking an active role in heritage management, educational institute can help ensure that cultural heritage sites like Lalmai-Mainamati are preserved for future generation to enjoy and learn from our past culture ruins heritage.

12. Reference:

1. Shrivastava, Dr. Shailaj Kumar (2016). Role of Educational institutions In promoting Social Awareness, International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies(IJIRAS),Volume 3, Issue 13,December 2016, ISSN: 2394-4404.
2. "Educational institution - Dictionary Definition". *Vocabulary.com*. Retrieved 2017-07-17.).
3. Ahmed, Manzoor, Rahman, Md Mostafizur,(2016), SDG4/Education 2030 and 7th five year plan of Bangladesh: Aliging National and global objectives strategies and indicators, Bangladesh Education Journal, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
4. Aas, C., Ladkin, A., & Fletcher, J. (2005). Stakeholder collaboration and heritage management. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 32(1), pp. 28–48. DOI: 10.1016/j.annals.2004.04.005
5. Bott, A. L., Grabowski, S., & Wearing, S., (2011). Stakeholder Collaboration in a Prospective World Heritage Area: The case of Kokoda and the Owen Stanley Ranges, *CosmopolitanCivil Societies Journal*, Vol.3, No.2, ISSN: 1837-5391, UTSe Press, Sydney, Australia.
6. Omar,H, Razak,N.H.A., Rawi,S.B.,& Ramely,A.(2018). The role of museum as a Cultural Heritage Attraction: Kota Kuala Kedah Museum. *Journal of Tourism & Hospitality and Environment management*. 3(7), 11-18.
7. Logan, W.,Wijesuriya, G. (2015). The New heritage studies and education, Training and capacity-building,A companion to heritage studies; DOI: 10.1002/9781118486634.CH37.
8. Lumley,R. (1988). The museum time-machine: putting culture on display. London Engand: Routledge.
9. Rahman, Md Mostagizur, Mohammed, Khadija, Akter, Nasrin, Chowdhury, Kamrul Qader (2020), the Role of Play in Pre-Primary Educational Setting of Bangladesh. *IJARIE-ISSN (O)-2395-4396*, Vol-6 issues -1 2020.
10. Jokilehto, J. 2006. "An International Perspective to Conservation Education." *Built Heritage Conservation Education Edited issue of Built Environment*, July 16

11. Safi, Yara.(2020), Role of Universities in preserving cultural heritage in areas of conflict, International Journal of cultural policy. December 2020, 27(7). DOI: 10.1080/10286632.2020.1857374.
12. Hassan, Md Nazmul (2022), Digitally Public Engagement in heritage safeguard and practice: A case study in Lalmai-Mainamati Hills Region, Bangladesh. 5th International Culture,Art and Literature congress, IKSad Publishing House, Turkey. ISBN: 978-625-6955-14-1.